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FIRM ATTRIBUTES AND DIVIDEND POLICY OF LISTED DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study examined the effect of firm attributes on the dividend policies of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria using firm leverage and firm liquidity as the proxy for independent variables. Ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. Data were extracted from annual report and accounts of the sampled banks in Nigeria. Multiple regression analysis was employed to test the hypotheses. The result of the study revealed that firm liquidity has no significant effect on the dividend payout at 5% level of significance, while leverage ratio has significant effect on the dividend payout. From the findings, this study recommended among others, that firm leverage has significant effect on dividend policies, there is need to maintain optimal leverage levels to balance capital adequacy requirements and ensure dividend sustainability and financial stability.

Keywords: Firm Attributes, Firm leverage, Firm liquidity and Dividend policy.

Introduction

Firm attributes provide an important lens for understanding dividend policy because they capture internal financial capacity and constraints. Profitability reflects a bank's ability to generate earnings from its asset base and operations; profitable banks are generally better positioned to pay dividends sustainably without eroding their capital base. Empirical evidence in the Nigerian banking context suggests that profitability tends to be positively associated with dividend payout ratios, consistent with the view that stronger earnings capacity supports higher payouts (Ademola et al., 2024). The dividend policy remains one of the most debated corporate finance decisions because it determines how much of a firm's earnings are distributed to shareholders and how much is retained to finance growth and strengthen capital. This "dividend puzzle" is particularly important in the banking sector, where profitability, leverage, liquidity, and size interact strongly with risk management and regulatory capital expectations (Mustapha & Abdullahi, 2023; Ademola et al., 2024).

In Nigeria, Depository Banks (DMBs) occupy a strategic position in the economy, serving as key conduits for financial intermediation, credit creation and stability in the payment system. Because banks mobilize deposits and turn them into loans and other assets, their operations are inherently sensitive to liquidity conditions and

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leverage patterns. A bank may report accounting profits but still face pressure from liquidity needs, credit risk provisioning, and capital adequacy requirements.

Consequently, dividend policy in banks is not merely a discretionary payout decision; it is also a financial stability issue with implications for depositor confidence, systemic risk, and investor perception (Ajiboye et al., 2024).

Leverage ratio the extent to which a bank relies on debt relative to equity also influences dividend policy.

While banks are naturally leveraged institutions due to deposit financing, high leverage may intensify risk and increase the need to retain earnings to strengthen equity buffers. From a risk and prudential perspective, excessive leverage may limit dividend payouts as regulators may prefer banks to rebuild capital rather than distribute profits (Ademola et al., 2024; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2025).

Thus, leverage often has a negative impact on dividend payouts when a higher debt burden increases financial pressure and reduces distributable income. Recent regulatory measures highlight the seriousness of the problem. For example, the Central Bank of Nigeria has issued supervisory guidelines that restrict the payment of dividends to banks operating under certain conditions, reflecting concerns over capital adequacy and sufficiency of provisions (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2025). Such regulatory measures imply that dividend policy in Nigerian banks is not purely a managerial preference but a decision shaped by firm-level financial conditions and the broader supervisory framework.

Yet, many stakeholders—including investors and analysts—still struggle to predict why some banks maintain higher payout ratios while others reduce or suspend dividends, even within the same industry and period. Empirically, although studies have examined dividend policy and bank performance, the results are not always consistent with respect to the role of key firm characteristics. Data suggests that profitability, liquidity and bank size can contribute to higher dividend payout ratios, while leverage can limit distributions (Ademola et al., 2024). Some related Nigerian studies focus on dividend policy and firm value or financial performance, rather than isolating how specific firm attributes jointly explain payout ratio decisions in the banking sector (Mustapha & Abdullahi, 2023; LJBFEI, 2024). Therefore, the problem addressed by this study was the limited and still inconclusive clarity on the extent to which leverage and liquidity explain the dividend payout ratio of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria in the contemporary period.

The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of firm attributes on the dividend policies of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

- I. Ascertain the effect of leverage ratio on the dividend payout ratio of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- II. Evaluate the effect of liquidity ratio on the dividend payout ratio of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Conceptual review

Firm Attributes

Firm attributes refer to internal characteristics of a firm that influence managerial decisions and financial outcomes.

In corporate finance literature, firm attributes such as profitability, leverage, liquidity, and firm size are widely used to explain variations in dividend policy across firms and over time (Denis & Osobov, 2008). These attributes reflect a firm's financial strength, risk profile, operational scale, and capacity to generate and distribute cash flows. In the banking context, firm attributes are particularly significant because they directly affect a bank's ability to meet regulatory requirements while rewarding shareholders. For example, a profitable bank can still

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limit its dividends if leverage is high or liquidity reserves are low. Emerging market studies consistently show that firm-specific characteristics have more influence in determining dividend policy than macroeconomic factors (Baker & Powell, 2012). Recent Nigerian evidence also supports the relevance of firm attributes in explaining dividend payout behavior among listed deposit money banks (Ademola et al., 2024).

Leverage Ratio

Leverage refers to the extent to which a firm finances its operations through debt relative to equity. In banking, leverage is inherent due to deposit mobilization; however, excessive leverage increases financial risk and may constrain dividend payments.

Empirical evidence generally supports a negative relationship between leverage and dividend payout. Aivazian et al. (2006) found that highly leveraged firms tend to pay lower dividends due to debt servicing obligations and restrictive debt covenants. In the banking context, Abreu and Gulamhussen (2013) reported that leverage negatively affects dividend payouts, particularly during periods of heightened regulatory scrutiny. For Nigerian deposit money banks, recent studies indicate that higher leverage ratios are associated with lower dividend payout ratios, reflecting the need to conserve capital and comply with prudential standards (Ademola et al., 2024). Regulatory interventions by the CBN further reinforce this relationship by limiting dividend payments for banks with weak capital positions (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2025).

Liquidity Ratio

Liquidity refers to a firm's ability to meet short-term obligations as they fall due. For banks, liquidity management is critical because of the maturity mismatch between deposits and loans. Dividend payments require cash outflows, making liquidity a key determinant of dividend policy. Firms with stronger liquidity positions are better able to sustain dividend payments without impairing operations (Baker & Powell, 2012). Empirical studies have reported mixed but generally positive relationships between liquidity and dividend payout. In early studies, Jensen (1986) argued that excess cash flow encourages dividend distribution to reduce agency costs. More recent banking studies suggest that adequate liquidity supports dividend stability, while liquidity stress leads to dividend reductions (Abreu & Gulamhussen, 2013).

In Nigeria, evidence indicates that liquidity ratio has a positive and significant effect on dividend payout among listed deposit money banks (Kumshe et al., 2021). This implies that banks with stronger liquidity buffers are more capable of meeting both operational needs and shareholder expectations. In banking, dividend policy is shaped by profitability, risk, liquidity, leverage, and regulatory oversight. Empirical evidence from Nigeria suggests that dividend payout ratios are positively influenced by profitability, liquidity, and firm size, but negatively affected by leverage (Ademola et al., 2024). These findings reflect the need for banks to balance shareholder returns with prudential requirements and long-term sustainability.

Empirical Review

Ademola, Al-Faryan, and Kazeem (2024) sought to identify the firm-specific and macroeconomic drivers of dividend payout ratio, with profitability treated as a key explanatory variable. The research adopted an ex post facto design, using secondary data sourced from the CBN Statistical Bulletin and audited annual financial statements. The study covered a long horizon; comparing periods associated with banking structural changes and included bank-level data across an extended timeframe (including pre- and post-merger eras). The authors applied descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and panel least square regression, supported by diagnostic procedures

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such as the Hausman test, and also reported stationarity testing procedures in their estimation workflow. Dividend payout ratio was measured as dividend paid relative to profit after tax. The findings indicated that profitability was positively associated with dividend payout ratio, implying that as bank profitability improves, banks are more able and more likely to distribute earnings to shareholders. Nguyen, Pham, and Vu (2024) examined how liquidity conditions influence dividend payout decisions among firms operating in emerging economies. The study adopted an ex post facto research design and utilized secondary panel data from non-financial firms listed across selected emerging markets over a ten-year period. Liquidity was proxied using the current ratio and cash flow measures, while dividend policy was measured using dividend payout ratio. Data were analyzed using panel regression techniques, including fixed and random effects estimators, supported by robustness checks. The study revealed that firms with stronger liquidity positions were more likely to pay higher and more stable dividends, while liquidity-constrained firms tended to reduce or omit dividend payments. Nguyen and Bui (2024) examined how firm-specific attributes, particularly firm size, influence dividend payout decisions in emerging market economies. The study adopted an ex post facto research design and used secondary panel data drawn from listed non-financial firms across selected ASEAN countries over a ten-year period. Firm size was measured using the natural logarithm of total assets, while dividend policy was proxied by the dividend payout ratio. Data were analyzed using panel regression techniques, including fixed-effects and random-effects estimators, with robustness checks for heteroskedasticity and endogeneity. The findings revealed that firm size has a positive and statistically significant effect on dividend payout, indicating that larger firms were more likely to pay higher and more stable dividends. Tuoyo, Ashaolu, Debo-Ajagunna, and Oladipo (2023) determined the relationship between dividend policy and bank performance, with particular attention to profitability indicators such as return on assets (ROA). The study relied on secondary data extracted from the financial statements of deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The study used descriptive statistics and multiple regression techniques to establish the nature and strength of relationships between dividend policy measures and performance variables. The study found a positive and statistically significant relationship between ROA and dividend per share, indicating that banks with stronger profitability relative to assets tended to pay higher dividends. Ademola and Oladipo (2023) ascertained whether firm size significantly influences dividend payout behavior among listed Nigerian firms across different sectors. The study employed an ex post facto research design and relied on secondary data extracted from the audited annual reports of firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. Data spanning several years were analyzed using multiple regression analysis within a panel data framework. The results showed that firm size exerted a positive and significant effect on dividend payout ratio, suggesting that larger firms were more consistent in dividend payments than smaller firms. The study concluded that firm size enhances dividend-paying capacity due to better cash flow stability and reduced business risk. Olorunfemi and Adegbite (2023) assessed whether liquidity management practices influence dividend payout decisions among listed manufacturing firms. The study adopted an ex post facto research design and relied on secondary data sourced from the annual reports of selected manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The authors employed multiple regression analysis to examine the effect of liquidity indicators—such as current ratio and cash ratio—on dividend payout. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between liquidity and dividend payout, indicating that firms with better liquidity management paid higher dividends. Cyril (2022) evaluated how profitability-related indicators earnings per share (EPS), return on assets (ROA), return on equity

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(ROE), and profit for the year influence dividend payout (proxied by dividend per share) among Nigerian deposit money banks spanning from 2011 to 2020. The method of analysis was regression analysis, supported by relevant descriptive statistics. The findings indicated that EPS had a significant positive effect on dividend per share, implying that as profitability per share increases, banks tend to reward shareholders through higher dividends. The study also reported that ROE was insignificant; suggesting that equity returns alone may not consistently drive dividend decisions within the sample and period. Cyril (2022) assessed how selected financial performance indicators—including leverage—affect dividend payout decisions of Nigerian deposit money banks. The study adopted an ex post facto research design and used secondary data obtained from the published financial reports of selected listed banks over the period 2011–2020. Regression analysis was employed to examine the relationships among the variables. The findings revealed that leverage had a significant negative relationship with dividend payout, suggesting that banks with higher leverage levels were constrained in their ability to distribute dividends. Rahman and Rashid (2022) investigated dividend policy determinants in their work titled “Firm Size, Ownership Structure and Dividend Policy: Evidence from Manufacturing Firms.” The primary objective of the study was to examine the effect of firm size and other firm attributes on dividend policy among manufacturing firms. The study adopted a panel research design using secondary data obtained from the annual reports of manufacturing companies listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange. Firm size was measured by the logarithm of total assets, while dividend policy was captured by dividend per share and payout ratio. The method of data analysis involved panel regression estimation. The findings indicated that firm size had a strong positive influence on dividend payout, implying that larger manufacturing firms were more likely to distribute dividends due to lower earnings volatility and greater market reputation. Kadioglu and Yilmaz (2017) in their study examined “Liquidity, Profitability, and Dividend Policy: Evidence from Turkish Firms.” The main objective of the study was to examine how liquidity and profitability jointly influence dividend policy decisions among non-financial firms. The study employed a panel data research design using secondary data from firms listed on the Istanbul Stock Exchange over a nine-year period. The authors applied panel regression analysis to estimate the relationships between liquidity ratios and dividend payout. The findings showed that liquidity had a significant positive effect on dividend payout, while firms with liquidity shortages were less likely to pay dividends. The study concluded that dividend policy is strongly dependent on the availability of liquid assets.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted an ex post facto research design. This design is considered appropriate because the study rely on historical financial data that already exist and cannot be manipulated by the researcher. The population of the study comprised all deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX).

Method of Data Collection

The study used secondary data, which were obtained from the published annual reports and audited financial statements of the listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Additional data were sourced from the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) and other relevant financial publications. The data collected cover variables such as dividend payout ratio, leverage ratio and liquidity ratio.

Method of Data Analysis

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The data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values were used to describe the characteristics of the variables. For inferential analysis, panel data regression techniques was employed to examine the effect of firm attributes on dividend policy. All hypotheses were tested at the 5% level of significance using relevant econometric software.

Model Specification

The study specified a panel regression model as follows:

$$DPO_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LEV_{it} + \beta_2 LIQ_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

- DPO_{it} = Dividend Payout of bank i in year t
- LEV_{it} = Leverage Ratio of bank i in year t
- LIQ_{it} = Liquidity Ratio of bank i in year t
- β_0 = Constant term
- $\beta_1 - \beta_2$ = Regression coefficients
- μ_{it} = Error term
- t = Time/period covered

Data Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	DPS	LEV	LIQ
Mean	10.36294	0.780822	1.873369
Median	0.094200	0.879733	1.416411
Maximum	250.9889	2.311605	9.714370
Minimum	0.000000	0.000000	-2.559569
Std. Dev.	45.61339	0.329263	1.905468
Skewness	4.445906	-0.644968	2.012340
Kurtosis	21.23819	8.154924	7.490918
Jarque-Bera	1869.786	128.2439	165.1640
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	1129.561	85.10955	204.1972
Sum Sq. Dev.	224702.8	11.70875	392.1271
Observations	109	109	109

Source: E-views 9.0 Analytical Result (2026)

Interpretation

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the different variables of the study with an observation and the mean which is the most commonly used measure of central tendency. The standard deviations show the variation from the mean, and it measure of risk, the higher the standard deviation, the higher the risk. The standard deviation is a measure that summarizes the amount by which every value within a dataset varies from the mean. Skewness is the measure of how much the probability distribution of a random variable deviates from the normal distribution. Table 1 delineates that the probability distribution for DPR (4.446), LIQ (2.012) is positively skewed distribution,

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while the probability distribution for LEV (-0.645) is negatively skewed distribution. The probability values of the Jarque-Bera Statistics revealed that DPR = 0.000; LEV = 0.000; and LIQ= 0.00 are statistically significant at 5%.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Matrix

	DPS	LEV	LIQ
DPS	1		
LEV	-0.30143	1	
LIQ	-0.16268	-0.02113	1

Source: E-Views 9 Correlation Output, 2026

From the findings on the correlation analysis in table 2, the study revealed that there is a negative relationship between LEV and LIQ and DPR by correlation factors of -0.301 and -0.163, respectively. Multicollinearity is the occurrence of high intercorrelations among two or more independent variables in a multiple regression model. Multicollinearity can lead to wider confidence intervals that produce less reliable probabilities in terms of the effect of independent variables in a model (Frost, 2021).

Test of Hypotheses

Table 3 Panel Least Square Regression Analysis testing the effect of LEV, LIQ and DPR

Dependent Variable: DPO

Method: Least Squares

Date: 02/21/26 Time: 08:32

Sample (adjusted): 1 125

Included observations: 109 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	50.93920	11.52308	4.420622	0.0000
LEV	-42.25298	12.62902	-3.345704	0.0011
LIQ	-4.048440	2.182285	-1.855138	0.0664
R-squared	0.119451	Mean dependent var		10.36294
Adjusted R-squared	0.102837	S.D. dependent var		45.61339
S.E. of regression	43.20441	Akaike info criterion		10.39690
Sum squared resid	197861.8	Schwarz criterion		10.47097
Log likelihood	-563.6310	Hannan-Quinn criter.		10.42694
F-statistic	7.189724	Durbin-Watson stat		1.131362
Prob(F-statistic)	0.001180			

Source: E-View 9.0

In table 3, the regression analysis was conducted to test the relationship between firm leverage (LEV), firm liquidity (LIQ), and dividend Payout (DPO). Adjusted R squared is coefficient of determination which tells us

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the changes in the dependent variable due to the changes in the independent variables. From the results, the value of adjusted R squared was 0.102, showing that there was variation of 10% on dividend per share due to changes in LEV and LIQ. This shows that 10% changes in dividend per share of the firms could be accounted for by independent variables; LEV and LIQ, while 90% was explained by unknown variables that were not included in the model.

The Durbin-Watson Statistic of 1.131 suggests that the model contain serial correlation. The F-statistic of the regression is equal to 7.189724 and the associated F-statistical probability is equal to 0.001, showing that leverage and liquidity have statistically significant effect on dividend Payout of the deposit money bank.

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: Leverage ratio has no significant effect on the dividend payout of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

The probability of the slope coefficients indicate that; P-value = 0.000 < 0.05). The co-efficient value of; $\beta_1 = -42.25298$; $t = -3.345704$, implies that leverage ratio has a significant effect on the dividend Payout of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria, and also statistically significant at 5%.

Since the P-value of 0.001 is less than the critical value of 5% (0.05), then, it would be upheld that leverage ratio has a significant effect on the dividend payout of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria at 5% level of significance.

Hypothesis 11

H₀₃: Liquidity ratio has no significant effect on the dividend payout of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

The probability of the slope coefficients indicate that; P-value = 0.07 > 0.05). The co-efficient value of; $\beta_1 = -4.048440$; $t = -1.855138$, implies that liquidity ratio has no significant effect on the dividend payout of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria, and also statistically significant at 5%.

Since the P-value of 0.07 is higher than the critical value of 5% (0.05), then, it would be upheld that liquidity ratio has a significant effect on the dividend payout of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria at 5% level of significance.

Discussion Conclusion

This study examined the effect of firm attributes on the dividend policies of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria using firm leverage and firm liquidity as the proxy for independent variables. Multiple regression analysis was employed to test the hypotheses. The result of the study revealed that firm liquidity has no significant effect on the dividend payout at 5% level of significance, while leverage ratio has significant effect on the dividend payout. From the data analyzed the study revealed that firm leverage has a negative significant effect on dividend payout and this is in line with Tuoyo, Ashaolu, Debo-Ajagunna, and Oladipo (2023); Abreu and Gulamhussen (2013) who showed that leverage exerted a negative and significant influence on dividend payout, indicating that banks with higher debt ratios were less likely to pay higher dividends. Ademola, Al-Faryan, and Kazeem (2024) who revealed that leverage had a negative statistically significant effect on dividend payout, implying that banks with higher debt exposure tended to retain earnings rather than distribute dividends.

The study conclusively, reported that dividend policy remains one of the most controversial decisions in corporate finance, as it determines how much of a company's profits are distributed to shareholders and how much is retained to fund capital growth and consolidation.

From the findings, this study recommended the followings;

1. The firm leverage has significant effect on dividend policies, there is need to maintain optimal leverage levels to balance capital adequacy requirements and ensure dividend sustainability and financial stability.

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2. Since the firm liquidity is significant with the bank dividend payout, the banks management needs to prioritize liquidity management to sustain dividend payments and to support stable dividend policies without compromising operational efficiency.

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